

Fig. 1. pH-metric and conductometric titration curves of CTA in absence and presence of Th(IV) and U(VI) with 0.1 M NaOH—Curves 1 & 1'—(1×10^{-3} M) CTA; Curves 2 & 2'—(1×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) Th(IV); Curves 3 & 3'—(2×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) Th(IV); Curves 4 & 4'—(1×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) UO_2^{2+} ; Curves 5 & 5'—(2×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) UO_2^{2+} .

The third set of titration also shows only two inflections as in the case of second set of titration suggesting that there is no possibility of 3 : 1 complexes. The reaction taking place in the whole process of titration may be represented as follows :

Set II :

Set III :

The formation of the complexes as discussed above have been verified by conductometric titrations. The observed plots (Fig. 1) confirm the formation of complexes as shown by equations given above.

References

1. C. K. SHARMA, V. D. GUPTA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 207.
2. R. WAKE, H. MIYATA and TOEIK, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1968, **41**, 1952.
3. A. BANERJEE and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 995.
4. S. S. DODWAD, M. G. DATAR and I. R. PATIL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **22A**, 89.
5. P. S. PRABHU and S. S. DODWAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 546.
6. M. S. KHARASCH and H. S. INBELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **53**, 2702.
7. P. S. PRABHU and S. S. DODWAD, Proceedings of Symposium on Fundamental and Applied Electrochemistry, March 1982, p. 87.

Effect of Acetic Acid on the Oxidation of Mandelic Acid by Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate

S. L. OSWAL* and (Miss) K. G. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 17 April 1982, revised 3 January 1983, accepted 27 October 1983

OXIDATION of mandelic acid (MA) has been investigated by different workers using several oxidizing agents. The kinetics of oxidation of MA by cerium(IV)¹⁻³, vanadium(V)⁴⁻⁶, manganese(III)⁷, peroxydisulphate⁸ and bromine⁹ has been studied in aqueous acidic media, and by chromic acid¹⁰⁻¹³ both in aqueous acidic media and in acetic acid-water binary mixtures. However, no data seems to have been reported on the kinetics of oxidation of MA by manganese(III) pyrophosphate. Manganese(III) pyrophosphate is a good selective one electron oxidant towards organic compounds. It has been widely used by Waters and coworkers¹⁴ to study the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of a variety of organic substrates. The investigations of Waters and coworkers were carried out in aqueous acidic medium, but as many organic compounds are insoluble in water their oxidation kinetics cannot be investigated in aqueous medium. One has to use other solvents like acetic acid, dioxane, acetonitrile, etc. Bakore and Narain¹⁵ had reported rate enhancement due to acetic acid in the oxidation of MA by chromic acid while our preliminary experiment showed retardation in the rate of oxidation due to the presence of acetic acid in reaction mixture for the oxidation of MA by manganese pyrophosphate. It was therefore, thought worthwhile to investigate in detail the oxidation of mandelic acid by manganese(III) pyrophosphate in

* Author for correspondence.

acetic acid-water binary mixtures of different compositions with a view to gaining insight into the mechanism of oxidation and role of acetic acid as a solvent. The effect of other solvent like dioxane has also been studied.

Experimental

Manganese(III) pyrophosphate was prepared and standardized by the method of Lingane and Karplus¹⁵. Mandelic acid (Amrut Lab. Chem.) was further purified by recrystallizations from water to give a melting point in accord with the literature value. All other chemicals used were B.D.H., A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Acetic acid B.D.H., A.R., was purified by refluxing over chromium oxide and subsequent fractional distillation¹⁶.

Reactions were carried out at constant temperature (with variations of $\pm 0.05^\circ$) and in acetic acid-water binary mixtures and also in aqueous acid media. The hydrogen ion concentration was adjusted by the addition of appropriate amount of dil. sulphuric acid solution. Toshniwal digital pH-meter, Type CL 46, was employed for pH measurements (sensitivity 0.01 unit) and calibrated for pH 4.05 and 9.18 using potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffers, respectively. [MA] and [H⁺] were always much in excess over that of [Mn(III) pyrophosphate]. Rates of oxidation were determined by measuring absorbance (O.D.) of Mn(III) at 520 nm using Systronic colorimeter, Type 101, Sr. N. 330. Pseudo first order rate constants (k₁) were calculated from the slopes of the linear log(O.D.) vs time plots (k₁ = -2.303 slope).

Results and Discussion

Under the kinetic conditions products of oxidation are benzaldehyde and CO₂. Benzaldehyde was identified as 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone and confirmed by m.p. and m.m.p.

The rate of oxidation of mandelic acid by Mn(III) pyrophosphate is slower in acetic acid-water or dioxane-water binary mixtures than in the aqueous medium. The oxidation was studied in acetic acid-water and dioxane-water mixtures of different compositions. With the increase in the proportions of acetic acid or dioxane, the rate of oxidation diminishes. These data are summarised in Table 1. The order with respect to oxidant

Mn(III) is one as is evident from the linear plot of log(O.D.) vs time for over 60% of the reaction and as well as by finding pseudo first order rate constants at different initial [Mn(III)] from 2 to 4×10^{-3} M, which are independent of the initial [Mn(III)]. The rate of oxidation increases with the increase in the concentration of MA (Table 2). A plot of 1/[MA] vs 1/k₁ is linear but does not pass

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MANDELIC ACID, PYROPHOSPHATE AND pH ON REACTION RATE

[Mn(III) = 0.004 M, solvent = 40% aq. acetic acid ; Temp. 303K

[MA] × 10 ³	[Pyrophosphate]	pH	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
1	0.0268	0.75	2.4
2	"	"	3.4
3	"	"	4.7
4	"	"	5.8
5	"	"	7.8
6	"	"	8.5
7	"	"	10.5
9	"	"	18.0
3	0.0346	"	3.1
3	0.0425	"	2.5
3	0.0582	"	2.1
3	0.0268	0.2	4.8
3	"	1.4	4.6
3	"	1.7	4.8
3	"	2.9	4.9

through the origin. Thus, the order with respect to mandelic acid varies as [MA]/{a+[MA]}. With the increase in the [pyrophosphate] the rate of oxidation decreases (Table 2) and the order with respect to free pyrophosphate concentration varies as 1/{b+[pyrophosphate]_{free}}. The values of a and b constants, obtained from graphical method, are 0.0245 and 0.00536, respectively. Rate of oxidation is not sensitive to the [H⁺] from pH 0.2 to 2.9 in acetic acid + water medium (Table 2). The addition of Mn(II) ions as manganous sulphate has no appreciable effect on the rate of oxidation of mandelic acid. Positive free radical test was obtained with the polymerization of acrylonitrile when added to the reaction mixture.

For the determination of thermodynamic parameters reaction was studied at various temperatures in the range of 299 to 318 K (Table 3) in the presence of acetic acid as well as in its absence. The enthalpy (ΔH^o), free energy (ΔG^o) and

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON REACTION RATE

{MA} = 0.03 M ; [Mn(III)] = 0.004, [Pyrophosphate] = 0.0268 M, pH = 0.75, Temp. 303K

Acetic acid %	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	Dioxane %	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0	10.9	0	10.9
10	9.2	20	5.1
20	7.3	40	1.8
30	5.5		
40	4.7		

TABLE 3—TEMPERATURE EFFECT OF THE RATE OF REACTION

[MA] = 0.08 M, [Mn(III)] = 0.004 M, [Pyrophosphate] = 0.0268 M, pH = 0.75

Temp. K	k, × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
	in 40% CH ₃ COOH	in aqueous medium
299	3.5	6.2
303	4.7	10.9
308	8.4	16.8
313	15.3	29.9
318	23.0	

entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) of activation in acetic acid-water medium are 80.7 kJ mol⁻¹, 88.6 kJ mol⁻¹ and -25.9 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ respectively. The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) in aqueous medium is 76.1 kJ mol⁻¹. The enthalpy of activation in both the media is almost the same indicating that acetic acid is not involved in the transition state of the rate determining step.

The effect of concentration of manganic pyrophosphate, mandelic acid and pyrophosphate on rate of oxidation of mandelic acid suggests that there is a fast reversible formation of a complex between Mn(III) pyrophosphate and mandelic acid with the displacement of pyrophosphate ligand as follows (eq. 1).

The rate determining step is breaking of complex with C-C cleavage and free radical formation (eq. 2)

The free radical $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{---}\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}(\text{OH})$ again reacts with Mn(III) forming benzaldehyde as follows (eq. 3)

The above proposed scheme (eqs. 1 to 3) would lead to the following rate expression (4)

$$-\frac{d[\text{Mn(III)}]}{dt} = \frac{k [\text{Mandelic acid}] [\text{Mn(III)}]}{\left\{ \frac{[\text{Pyrophosphate}]}{K} + [\text{Mandelic acid}] \right\}} \quad \text{(4)}$$

The rate expression is quite consistent with the experimentally observed rate data. The decrease in the rate of oxidation due to increase in either acetic acid or dioxane concentration may be due to the effect of dielectric constant of the medium. The solvent effect suggests that the reaction may be of dipole-dipole type. Thus, the manganic pyrophosphate species involved in the reaction may be $[\text{Mn(III)}(\text{H}_3\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_3]$ rather than $[\text{Mn(III)}(\text{H}_3\text{P}_3\text{O}_7)_3]^{3-}$ to account for the observed effect of solvent. The value of enthalpy of activation, 80.7 kJ mol⁻¹, corresponds to C-C bond fission and supports the formation of benzaldehyde as the product of oxidation.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K. G. P.) thanks South Gujarat University, Surat, for the award of a University Research Fellowship.

References

1. B. KRISHNA and K. C. TEWARI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3097.
2. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1192.
3. R. DAYAL and G. V. BAKORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1098.
4. J. R. JONES, W. A. WATERS and J. S. LITTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 680.
5. R. SHANKAR and S. N. SWAMI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, 31, 11.
6. R. SHANKAR and S. N. SWAMI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 105.
7. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1489.
8. G. V. BAKORE and S. N. JOSHI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1971, 73, 198.
9. P. AUKETT and I. R. L. BARKER, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin Trans. II*, 1973, 965.
10. G. V. BAKORE and S. NARAIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 3419.
11. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3193.
12. F. B. BECKWITH and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 929.
13. D. IP and J. ROCEK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 6311.
14. K. B. WIBERG, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Academic Press, 1965, Vol. 5A, Chap. III and references therein.
15. J. J. LINGANE and R. KARPLUS, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 191.
16. W. C. EICHELBERGER and V. K. LAMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 55, 3638.

Synthesis and Biological Activities of Derivatives of Mercaptobenzimidazoles. Part-II : Some Reactions of 2-Mercapto-5 (or 6)-Nitro and 2-Mercapto-4 (or 7)-Nitrobenzimidazoles

V. MADHUSUDHAN RAO and V. MALLA REDDY*
University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 5 June 1981, revised 28 June 1983,
accepted 15 September 1983

THE syntheses and biological activities of certain perhydrothiazino-, perhydrothiazolobenzimidazoles and thiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazole-3(2H)-ones and their benzylidene derivatives have been reported¹⁻⁷. As a part of our studies on substituted mercaptobenzimidazoles⁸, we report here some cyclization reactions of 2-mercapto-4 (or 7)-nitro and 2-mercapto-5 (or 6)-nitrobenzimidazoles (Scheme 1), and the biological activities of the products.

2-Mercapto-5 (or 6)-nitro and 2-mercapto-4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazoles (IIa, b) have been synthesized by adopting a standard procedure⁹, starting from 4-nitro-, and 3-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines (Ia, b), respectively. The reaction of II with 1,2-dibromoethane resulted in the formation of a single product